

ISic0310

I.Sicily inscription 0310

Language

Latin

Type

funerary; honorific

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR141128

1. Q (uintus) Lutati [us---]
2. q (uaestor) d (ecreto) d (ecurionum) aedil [is---]
3. pro hono [re IIviratus duoviratus]
4. [tr]iclin [---- - ----]
5. t[rib]us l [ectis dedit ---]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491517

EDR 141128

EDCS 21900345

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae

Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7026 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Manganaro, G. 1989. Iscrizioni Latine nuove e vecchie della Sicilia. *Epigraphica*. 51: 161-196. At 173 no.44

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